

D8.1 Project Website

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MOIRAI

www.moirai-project.eu

Multiscale Ocean models and Information for climate Risk Assessment and Impact mitigation.

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Project Website

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1.0	30.04.2025	Reviewed Final version submitted to EC	Coordinator(s)

DISSEMINATION LEVEL		
PU	Public, fully open	X
SEN	Sensitive limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	
Classified R-UE/EU-R	EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444	
Classified C-UE/EU-C	EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444	
Classified S-UE/EU-S	EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444	

DELIVERABLE TYPE		
R	Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)	
DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs	
DEC	Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.	x
DATA	Data sets, microdata, etc.	
DMP	Data management plan	
ETHICS	Deliverables related to ethics issues.	
SECURITY:	Deliverables related to security issues	
OTHER:	Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.	

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Horizon Europe programme requires all projects to carry out Dissemination and Exploitation of their results as well as Communication of their project.

Communication in MOIRAI is a cross-cutting activity that is strategically planned with a view to the impacts we want to bring about. Following a coherent communication and dissemination plan (D8.2) addressing focused activities, MOIRAI will raise awareness and engagement around our comprehension and mitigation of climate-related challenges.

The MOIRAI website (<https://moirai-project.eu/>) is one of the main channels for communication of all project-relevant information, such as public downloadable products, news and events related to the project work scope. The website also provides basic information regarding the project beneficiaries and links to their websites. The website follows the EC guidelines to support the activities of the project, promote communication among all partners and be a vehicle of promotion of the project to the "external world".

The website went live on 01 April 2025 (M6) of the MOIRAI project, and it will continue to be updated throughout the project. These revisions will be particularly important in supporting communication and dissemination, and for ensuring maximum exploitation of the project results.

Acknowledgements:

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Introduction

1.1. Objectives of MOIRAI

MOIRAI, named after the three Greek goddesses of fate, stands as a pioneering project at the intersection of past, present, and future. MOIRAI weaves a comprehensive understanding of the ocean's dynamics and biogeochemical cycles through advanced models, integrating historical data, current observations, and future projections. Integrated into the frameworks of Destination Earth (DE) and the European Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO), MOIRAI will significantly advance our comprehension and mitigation of climate-related challenges.

The specific objectives are as follows:

1. Advance the representation and understanding of basin- and coastal- scale, ocean dynamics and biogeochemical cycle.
2. Build the capability to provide relevant ocean climate and risk services for different end-users, allowing for its replication in all SIX European seas.
3. Ensure MOIRAI model suite's interoperability with Destination Earth (DE) and European Digital Twin Ocean (European DTO) by deploying a new workflow management solution for i) reproducible modelling experimentation; ii) REASSHORE and its deployment in six use cases.
4. Build an interactive platform, REASSHORE, dedicated to two target groups: i) end-users (3 modules for the blue economy) and ii) policymakers (a science-to-policy indicators dashboard) who will be trained on the hub during a dedicated workshop.
5. Perform life cycle costing and life-cycle assessment of MOIRAI's solutions deployment in each of the six use cases guaranteeing MOIRAI's sustainable approach.

Figure 1 - MOIRAI work package PERT chart.

The project is comprised of eight work packages (WP), as shown in Figure 1. WP1 deals with project management and coordination, WP2 works on refined climate and ocean physics models for regional seas, WP3 develops improved regional Biogeochemical (BGC) and ecosystem models for coastal services, WP4 develops multi-scale coastal models for impact and risk assessment, WP5 looks at model uncertainty quantification and high-performance computing (HPC) optimization, WP6 provides decision support tools, WP7 provides demonstrations, validation and feedback; and WP8 is dedicated to communication, dissemination, synergies and policy recommendations.

1.2. Objectives of WP8

This document (D8.1) describes the MOIRAI website. The website supports all the activities in the project, especially those that relate to WP8 – Communication, Dissemination, Synergies and Policy recommendations. The main messages of the project and the other complimentary communication and dissemination channels are fully described in Deliverable 8.2 - Communication and Dissemination Plan.

The main objectives of WP8 are to:

- raise the visibility of the project and the environmental challenges it aims to address.

- promote and share project results among the scientific communities and end users.
- engage with a range of stakeholders including decision-makers, civil society, and other interested parties.
- support and promote the uptake and exploitation of the project results, providing all the necessary conditions for replicability and scale-up of the proposed solutions.
- emphasize EC's investment in finding solutions to climate challenge.

This website, together with social media, will provide a reference point for the project going forward, providing information on all the most relevant and up-to-date information from the project and in support of stakeholder engagement.

1.3. Organisation of the Report

This document provides a simple introduction to the MOIRAI website. The full website can be viewed online: <https://moirai-project.eu/>

2. MOIRAI Public Website

2.1 Purpose of MOIRAI Public Website

One domain has been purchased for MOIRAI, which is easy to identify, <https://moirai-project.eu/>. The URL leads the users to the homepage of the website. The MOIRAI website was developed during the first semester of 2025 and went live on 01 April 2025. A Google Analytics account is associated with the website to track the use statistics over time.

The MOIRAI public website supports all aspects of the project's dissemination, exploitation and communication (DEC) strategy as follows:

Dissemination ensures that the results and new findings of the project are easily findable and reach communities that need and can use them.

Exploitation ensures the results and products of the project are made available in such a way that they are easily used and re-used by others, ensuring that the project has a practical application that can be used immediately by the stakeholders who need those resources.

Communication ensures the flow of information about the project to a general or mixed audience, to inform society about the objectives, activities and achievement of the project throughout its entire lifecycle, as well as with the flow of information among the project consortium.

The MOIRAI public website provides a source of content for social media, allowing a longer lifespan of project material than the fast-paced social media sites allow. This means that social media posts will preferentially link to more permanent content that is

available for posterity on the MOIRAI website long after it has disappeared from the social media feeds.

2.2 Main Target Audiences

Main target audiences for the MOIRAI website (see D8.2 for more detail):

A. Academia:

- Coastal impact and risk experts
- Global and regional ocean-climate modelling communities
- Marine biologists and ecologist
- Operational forecasting community

B. Private Sector:

- Aquaculture farmers
- Offshore renewable energies
- Port activities
- Ship operators
- Multi-scale fisheries
- Touristic sector

C. Public Sector:

- Local and territorial decision-makers
- EU and National public authorities

D. Civil Society

- Coastal communities and NGOs

The website must appeal to the general public, assuming no previous knowledge of ocean and climate models, predictions, coastal hazards, and other MOIRAI themes, but also provide enough detail to be appreciated by academics, operational personal, and local and regional authorities, and decision makers. As such, the website must guarantee universal appeal as much as possible.

The main messages for these audiences as well as means of measuring impacts of communication and dissemination are thoroughly described in Deliverable 8.2 Communication and Dissemination Plan.

2.3 Main Specifications of the MOIRAI website

The objective was to create a website for MOIRAI that reflects the project image and its objectives. The design specifications were:

- be in line with the project branding (logo/look) (Figure 2),
- reflect the communication strategies for attracting the main target audiences and general public,
- have a simple, clean, appealing design,
- be responsive to different devices (desktop, mobile and tablet).
- simple structure, user friendly, and easy to navigate (few menu levels).

These complemented the technical specifications, which were as follows:

- Website only in one language (EN),
- Back office in WordPress or similar,
- Integration with Google Analytics and Search Console,
- Integration with social media (icons),
- Responsive interface,
- Optimized for the most widely used browsers, e.g. Google Chrome, Mozilla Firefox, Opera, Safari, Internet Explorer, Microsoft Edge, Opera, Brave, etc.
- Function in any operating system (Microsoft, Apply, Linux, etc.),
- SEO (Search Engine Optimization),
- Integration of newsletter subscription,
- Cookies notification,
- GDPR compliant.

Figure 2 - MOIRAI brand variations.

2.4 Hosting

The MOIRAI website is hosted on the cloud under a third-party agreement for a minimum of four years, beginning in 2025.

2.5 Website Homepage and Menus

Special attention was given to the design of the homepage as this is the page with the most immediate impact and sets the tone for the rest of the website. The website had to be clean and simple but also visually appealing and invite visitors to browse and explore. The main elements of the homepage were:

The Homepage features the following scrollable areas:

- **Header:** Highly prominent,
- **Highlights carousel:** a series of clickable images that take the visitor directly to specific areas of the site with updates, special achievements, new information, etc. These images change/rotate automatically and manually. This area is editable and may have more or fewer featured images (up to 5), with the possibility in the back office to add, remove, and define their order.
- **Brief description of the project:** A simple statement about MOIRAI.

- **News and Events:** with featured news that aims to give emphasis three articles or events on the project. This area is a preview of the full news area accessible from the main menu.
- **Newsletter subscription form:** allows visitors to sign up for the MOIRAI newsletter.
- **Header:** very clean and simple featuring the MOIRAI logo, the main menu (see below) and a search area.
- **Footer:** containing the EC flag and disclaimer (essential), social media links/icons, privacy and cookies policies, and contact button.

The homepage is shown in Figure 3. An example of an internal page is shown in Figure 4.

As mentioned above, the website was intended to have a simple structure with few menu levels (Figure 5). The main menu items were:

About: Objectives and Impacts; Partners; Management Structure; External Advisory Board; End Users.

Use Cases: Rethymno – Coastal Risk; Western Mediterranean – Blue Economy; North Sea – Coastal Risk; North Sea – Blue Economy; Greenland – Coastal Risk; Greenland-Scotland Ridge – Blue Economy.

Results: Deliverables, Publications, Training Materials; Communication Materials; Other Resources.

Applications: Impact Assessment; Risk and Damage Prediction; Vulnerability and Resilience Assessment Framework (VRAF); Model Optimization; Model Testing and Validation; Ocean-Climate Indicators; Early Warning System.

REASSHORE: About REASSHORE.

News: News, Press Releases.

Figure 3 - MOIRAI website homepage.

MOIRAI

ABOUT ▾ USE CASES ▾ RESULTS ▾ APPLICATIONS ▾ REASSHORE ▾ NEWS & EVENTS ▾

< back

Driving Change with the Launch of MOIRAI!

The MOIRAI team gathered in Athens, Greece from 7-8 January 2025 to formally launch this special project. MOIRAI (Multiscale Ocean models and Information for climate Risk Assessment and Impact mitigation), named after the three Greek goddesses of fate, stands as a pioneering project at the intersection of past, present, and future. MOIRAI weaves a comprehensive understanding of the ocean's dynamics and biogeochemical cycles through advanced models, integrating historical data, current observations, and future projections.

Funded through the European Union HORIZON programme (GA 101180994), MOIRAI answers the call to better understand ocean dynamics and biogeochemical (BGC) cycles. Marine BGC cycles are pathways for the movement of chemical substances and elements in marine environments. Understanding these cycles is crucial for developing climate models in European seas. MOIRAI aims to enhance our understanding of ocean dynamics and BGC cycles through advanced modelling, integrating historical data, current observations and future projections.

Aligned with Destination Earth and the European Digital Twin of the Ocean, MOIRAI will improve climate models for regional and coastal European seas, bridging the gap between operational and regional models. By enhancing climate modelling and prediction across the estuarine, coastal and open sea continuum the project will promote climate change resilience in coastal areas.

Under the leadership of National Technical University of Athens (NTUA), MOIRAI's consortium gathers 15 partners from 6 different countries, bringing an unprecedented, highly qualified, independent take on ocean models for climate predictions fuelling future mitigation and adaptation strategies.

You can find out more about MOIRAI by exploring this website or by checking out our CORDIS Profile. (<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101180994>)

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Figure 4 - Sample internal page from the News section.

Figure 5 - MOIRAI website plan. Items outlined in red were not included in the final version of the website.

2.5.1 Access to MOIRAI Deliverables and Other Resources

Project deliverables, training material, and other digital resources will be made available through the MOIRAI Zenodo community¹, to guarantee their long-term preservation. Common search engines such as Google Scholar and Microsoft Research are harvesting metadata for assets hosted at Zenodo and provide high visibility. The consortium will make available information relating to methods and tools with test datasets, and open reports produced within the project through the MOIRAI Zenodo Community.

The public website serves to provide a bridge between the project’s audience and the data hub. The benefit to storing data and other products on the Zenodo platform is that Zenodo automatically links each deposited research object to DataCite servers. Open data and publications produced in MOIRAI will be identifiable and locatable by a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) in order to make content easily and uniquely citable. A full explanation of the MOIRAI data management strategy is provided in D1.1 – Data Management Plan.

¹ <https://zenodo.org/communities/moirai>

3. Concluding Remarks

The MOIRAI public website and materials for dissemination and communication are essential elements to the project's Communication and Dissemination (D&C) Plan (D8.2). The website is the anchor for all other D&C products as it is the central point from which all other materials can be accessed. All MOIRAI products contain the website address, and a domain name has been chosen that is easy to remember, or to determine, if needed.

MOIRAI website and materials are supplemented with a suite of D&C channels, including social media, a data repository, and in-person activities that work together to promote the project, share information about the tools and methods used, share the project results, and most importantly, allow others to access and use the project outputs. All these tools and channels are in line with EC regulations, including GDPR.

MOIRAI

This report is made under the project
Multiscale Ocean models and Information for climate Risk Assessment and Impact
mitigation (MOIRAI).

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Danmarks
Meteorologiske
Institut

**Barcelona
Supercomputing
Center**
Centro Nacional de Supercomputación

